

Religion Philosophy of Mahatma Gandhi

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Introduction

Mohandas Karamchand Gandhi was born on 2 October 1869-30 January 1948 was the pre-eminent political and ideological leader of India during the Indian independence movement. He pioneered Satyagraha. This is defined as resistance to tyranny through mass civil disobedience, a philosophy firmly founded upon ahimsa or total non-violence. This concept helped India to gain independence, and inspired movements for civil rights and freedom across the world. Gandhi is often referred to as Mahatma Gandhi "Great Soul" an honorific first applied to him by Rabindranath Tagore. In India, he is also called Bapu, 2 October is commemorated there as Gandhi Jayanti, a national holiday, and worldwide as the International Day of Non-Violence. Gandhi was assassinated on 30 January 1948 by Nathuram Godse, a Hindu Nationality.

The Gandhian religion is not merely for Hindus, not merely for India, but for the whole world. The Gandhian philosophy is not only essential for the rebirth of the Indian nation but also for the re-education of the human race. It is becoming clear that at this supremely dangerous moment in human history, the only hope for mankind is Mahatma Gandhi's principle of non-violence. The Gandhi's Ahimsa, peace and non-aggression are the hallmarks of Gandhian Doctrine. Many years have gone by but the luster of the Gandhian religion remain undimmed. Invading forces have descended on India but Gandhi's ideals have remained. The ultimate destiny. The Gandhian religion, which is primarily concerned with spiritual development is of special significance in our age, which is marked by the obsolescence of the materialistic civilization. In fact, Gandhi laid the foundation of mathematical and scientific knowledge.

They measured both time and space. Let us look at some of basic conclusions reached by ancient insights, which have become the fundamentals of the modern Gandhian Philosophy. Gandhiji perceived the principle more clearly and understood its implication even more deeply.

The virtues of self-discipline, self restraint and self-development which are the main-stay of India Dharma and Gandhi's culture are as fully relevant today as they were many years ago. Therefore we must go all out to preserve the Gandhian religion. In fact Gandhi was a great soul who preached the essential unity of all religions and the basis unity of all humanity. In recent times unity has been sought to be undermined by forces, internal as well as external out to destabilize us. So it is now time for India to show the world that we are one as a society, are too secure in our spiritual strength and national heritage to be so easily uprooted. This is a gigantic task but we have not stirred it.

In India we are a highly religious society, wholly secular in character. Gandhi was deeply religious person but he was clear in mind that the state should be secular. He stood for the maximum possible distance between religious concerns of individuals and the state's obligations towards its citizens, Gandhi also clearly stated that secularism did not mean opposition to religion. He also said that the state had to honor all religions equally without attaching itself to a particular faith.

Strange as it may seem, there is a religious essence at the core of secularism and even the modern secular. West has recognized it. In Europe it has permitted all spheres of life and even the French speak of there being something eternal about religion as the basis of life. It has been universally accepted that secularism is not a denial of religion. On the contrary it means tolerance and respect for all religions what one can call the hospitality of faiths.

Gandhi's religious quest for truth had no geographical limits. His political activities were but an avocation to his religious mission. The centre-most point of Gandhi's religious philosophy is the inviolable sacredness of life and the consequent sinfulness of bloodshed. "Since we have no power to create, we have no power to destroy" was his belief.

Gandhi taught us, learning in the quest for national integration-is the crying need of the hour. Thus both as an ideology and as a policy, Gandhian religion acquired worldwide acceptance. Along with Mahatma Gandhi, other Indian leaders also contributed to strengthening of the secular spirit of India.

Faith

Gandhi was born a Hindu and practiced Hinduism all his life. As a common Hindu, he believed all religions to be equal, and rejected all efforts to convert him to a different faith. He was an avid theologian and read extensively about all major religions. He had the following to say about Hinduism:

Hinduism as I know it entirely satisfies my soul fills my whole being.... When doubts haunt me, when disappointments stare me in the face, and when I see not one ray of light on the horizon, I turn to the Bhagavad Gita and find a verse to comfort me; and immediately begin to smile in the midst of overwhelming sorrow. My life has been full of tragedies and if they have not left any visible and indelible effect on me, I owe it to the teachings of the Bhagavad Gita. Gandhi Smriti (The house Gandhi lodged in the last 4 months of his life has now become a monument, New Delhi). Gandhi wrote a commentary on the Bhagavad Gita in Gujarati. The Gujarati manuscript was translated into English by Mahadev Desai, who provided an additional introduction and commentary. It was published with a Foreword by Gandhi in 1946. Gandhi believed that at the core of every religion was truth and love (compassion, nonviolence and the Golden Rule). He also questioned what he saw as hypocrisy, malpractices, and dogma in all religions, including his own, and he was a tireless advocate for social reform in religion. Some of his comments on various religions are:

Thus if I could not accept Christianity either as a perfect or the greatest religion neither was I then convinced of Hinduism being such. Hindu defects were pressingly visible to me. If untouchability could be a part of Hinduism, it could but be a rotten part or as excrescence. I could not understand the *raison d'etre* of a multitude of sects and castes. What was the meaning of saying that the Vedas were the inspired Word of God? If they were inspired, why not also the Bible and the Quran? As Christian friends were endeavouring to convert me, so were Muslim friends. Abdullah Seth had kept on inducing me to study Islam, and of course he had always something to say regarding its beauty.

Gandhi's Autobiography

As soon as we lose the moral basis, we cease to be religious. There is no such thing as religion over-riding morality. Man, for instance, cannot be untruthful, cruel or incontinent and claim to have God on his side. The sayings of Muhammad are a treasure of wisdom, not only for Muslims but for all of mankind. I like your Christ; I do not like your Christians. Your Christians are so unlike your Christ.

God has no religion

Later in his life, when he was asked whether he was a Hindu, he replied, "Yes I am. I am also a Christian, a Muslim, a Buddhist and a Jew." In spite of their deep reverence to each other, Gandhi and Rabindranath Tagore engaged in protracted debates more than once. These debates exemplify the philosophical differences between the two most famous Indians at the time. On 15 January 1934, an earthquake hit Bihar and caused extensive damage and loss of life. Gandhi maintained this was because of the sin committed by upper caste Hindus by not letting untouchables in their temples (Gandhi was committed to the cause of improving the fate of untouchables, referring to them as Harijans, people of Krishna). Tagore vehemently opposed Gandhi's stance, maintaining that an earthquake can only be

caused by natural forces, not moral reasons, however repugnant the practice of untouchability may be Gandhi took a keen interest in theosophy. He empathized with theosophy's message of universal brotherhood and consequence.

Racism and Controversy

Some of Gandhi's early South African articles are controversial. On 7 March 1908, Gandhi wrote in the Indian Opinion of his time in a South African prison: "Kaffirs are as a rule uncivilized - the convicts even more so. They are troublesome, very dirty and live almost like animals." Writing on the subject of immigration in 1903, Gandhi commented: "We believe as much in the purity of race as we think they do...We believe also that the white race in South Africa should be the predominating race." During his time in South Africa, Gandhi protested repeatedly about the social classification of blacks with Indians, whom he described as "undoubtedly infinitely superior to the Kaffirs."Remarks such as these have led some to accuse Gandhi of racism. It is worth noting through that the word Kaffir had a different connotation in Gandhi's time than its current day meaning.

Two professors of history who specialise in South Africa, Surendra Bhana and Goolam Vahed, examined this controversy in their text, *The Making of a Political Reformer; Gandhi in South Africa, 1893-1914*. (New Delhi: Manohar, 2005). They focus in Chapter 1, "Gandhi, Africans and Indians in Colonial Natal" on the relationship between the African and Indian communities under "White rule" and policies which enforced segregation (and, they argue, led to inevitable conflict between these communities). Of this relationship they state that, "the young Gandhi was influenced by segregationist notions prevalent in the 1890s." At the same time, they state, "Gandhi's experiences in jail seemed to make him more sensitive to their plight.... the later Gandhi mellowed; he seemed much less categorical in his expression of prejudice against Africans, and much more open to seeing points of common cause. His negative views in the Johannesburg jail were reserved for hardened. African prisoners rather than Africans generally." However, when plans to unvoit a statue of Gandhi in Johannesburg was announced, a movement unsuccessfully tried to block it because of Gandhi's "racist" statements.

Role in Zulu War of 1906

In 1906, after the British introduced a new poll-tax, Zulus in South Africa killed two British officers. In response the British declared war against the Zulus. Gandhi actively encouraged the British to recruit Indians. He argued that Indians should support the war efforts in order to legitimize their claims to full citizenship. The British, however, refused to commission Indians as army officers: Nonetheless, they accepted Gandhi's offer to let a detachment of Indians volunteer as a stretcher-bearer corps to treat wounded British soldiers. This corps was commanded by Gandhi. On 21 July 1906, Gandhi wrote in *Indian Opinion*: "The corps had been formed at the instance of the Natal Government by way of

experiment, in connection with the operations against the Natives consists of twenty three Indians." Gandhi urged the Indian population in South Africa to join the war through his columns in Indian Opinion: "If the Government only realized what reserve force is being wasted, they would make use of it and give Indians the opportunity of a thorough training for actual warfare."

Mahatma Gandhi on Hinduism

I had practiced Hinduism from early childhood. My nurse had taught me to invoke Rama when I feared evil spirits. Later on I had come in contact with Christians, Muslims and other and after making a fair study of other religions, had stuck to Hinduism. I am as firm in my faith today as in my early childhood.

I believe god would make me an instrument of saving the religion that I love, cherish and practice. In any case, one has to have constant practice and acquaintance with the fundamentals of religion before being qualified for becoming god's instrument.

It has been whispered that by being so much with Musalman friends I make myself unfit to know the Hindu mind. The Hindu mind is myself. Surely I do not need to live amidst Hindus to know the Hindu mind when every fiber of my being is Hindu. My Hinduism must be a very poor thing if it cannot flourish under influences of the most adverse. I know instinctively what is necessary for Hinduism. As my instinct is wholly Hindu, I know that what I am about to say will be acceptable to the vast mass of the Hindus.

My Hinduism is not sectarian. It includes all that I know to be best in Islam, Christianity, Buddhism and Zoroastrianism. I approach politics, as everything else, in a religious spirit. Truth is my religion and ahimsa is the only way of its realization. I have rejected once and for all the doctrine of the sword. My position is and has been clear. I am proud of being a Hindu, but I have never gone to anybody as a Hindu to secure Hindu-Muslim unity. My Hinduism demands no pacts. I am no politician in the accepted sense.

It is because I am sanatani (orthodox) Hindu that I claim to be a Christian, a Buddhist and a Muslim. Some Muslim friends also feel that I have no right to read Arabic verses from the Quran, but such (people) do not know that true religion transcends language and scripture. I do not see any reason why I should not read the Kalma, why I should not praise Allah and why I should not acclaim Muhammad as his prophet. I believe in all the great prophets and saints of every religion. I shall continue to ask good to give me strength not to be angry with my accusers, but to be prepared even to die at their hands without wishing them ill. I claim that Hinduism is all inclusive and I am sure that if I live up to my convictions, I shall have served not only Hinduism but Islam also. There is mention of terrible punishments in the Bhagavatam, the Manu Smriti and the Vedas. Yet the central teaching of the Hindu

religion is that mercy of kindness is the essence of all religion. I want you to bear in mind what Tulsidas has said:

"Good and bad, all men are the creation of god. The man of good picks up the good and discards the bad like the proverbial san which is able to drink the milk and leave behind water, when a mixture of water and milk is placed before it."

I am proud to belong to than Hinduism which is all inclusive and which stands for tolerance. Aryan scholars swore by what they called the vedic religion and Hindustan is otherwise known as Aryavarta. I have no such aspiration. The Hindustan of my conception is all sufficing for me. It certainly includes the Vedas, but it includes also much more.

Tulsidas has summed it up in one doha: The root of religion is embedded in mercy, whereas egotism is rooted in love of the body. Tulsi says that mercy should never be abandoned, even though the body perishes.

Hinduism is not an exclusive religion. In there is room for the worship of all prophets in the world. It is not a missionary religion in the ordinary sense of the term. It has not doubt absorbed many tribes in its folds, but this absorption has been an evolutionary, imperceptible character. Hinduism tells everyone to worship god according to his own faith or dharma and so it lives at peace with all religions.

Though I call myself a sanatani Hindu, I am proud of the fact that the late Imam Saheb of South Africa accompanied me to India on his return and died in the Sabarmati ashram. His daughter and son-in-law are still at Sabarmati. Am I to throw them overboard? My Hindusim teaches me to respect all religions. In this lies the secret of RamaRaj.

The die is case for me. The common factor of all religions in non-violence. Some uncalculated more of it than others; all agree that you can never have too much of it. We must be sure, however, that it is non-violence and not a cloak for cowardice. Hinduism with its message of ahimsa is to me the most glorious religion in the world as my wife to me is the most beautiful woman in the world but others may feel the same about.

Religion is outranged when an outrage is perpetrated in its name. Almost all the riots in the unhappy land take place in the name of religion though they might have a political motive behind them. There is no room for goondaism in any religion worth the name, be it Islam, Hinduism or any other.

If religion dies, then India dies. Today the Hindus and the Muslims are clinging to the husk of religion. They have gone mad. But I hope that all this is forth, that all this scum has come to the surface, as happens when the waters of two rivers meet. Everything appears muddy on top and underneath is crystal clear and calm. The sucum goes to the sea of itself, and the rivers mingle and flow clear and pure.

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